

Role of Fintech Startups in Economic Growth with Special Reference to Phoebe

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Abstract

Fintech startups are known for their innovative approach to financial products and services. PhonePe, for example, offers a range of services beyond basic digital payments, including mutual fund investments, insurance, and more. This innovation encourages consumers to explore and use a variety of financial instruments, contributing to the growth of the financial sector. Financial services have been hit hard by cyber commotion, but it also opened up a host of new opportunities for people from all walks of life. This digital disruption has pushed us people further on the track of monetary enclosure, which now stood as a key In the previous span, this was a popular topic of discussion in India all thanks and credit goes to the leader's growing willingness for fiscal insertion within marginalized groups.

Keywords: Financial Products, Financial Innovation, Fintech

Introduction

Fintech is a term that refers to the mix of "Financial Technology" and "Innovation Methods of Delivering Financial Services." Traditional methods of providing financial services are being challenged by these technologies. (Mogaji, Nguyen, 2022) Financial services are improved and automated with this technology. Specialized software and algorithms make the financial services process easier for business users. (Zeidy, 2022). Technological disruption in the financial industry has boosted economic growth by creating millions of jobs and allowing marginalized people to access financial services, from establishing an account in a bank to acquiring advances/ loan without leaving a turn-up on notepaper.

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Here are some key ways in which fintech startups, with special reference to PhonePe, contribute to economic growth:

Financial Inclusion: Fintech startups often focus on providing financial services to the unbanked or underbanked population. (Ediagbonya, Tioluwani, 2023) By leveraging mobile technology, apps like PhonePe make it easier for individuals who may not have access to traditional banking services to participate in the formal economy. This helps in reducing economic disparities and promoting financial inclusion.

Digital Payments and Transactions: Fintech companies, especially those in the digital payments sector like PhonePe, facilitate quick and secure transactions. (Pallathadka & Pallathadka, 2022) This contributes to the efficiency of the overall economy by reducing the reliance on cash transactions, which can be cumbersome and costly. Digital payments also enhance transparency and help in curbing the informal economy. (Oh, E.Y, Zhang, 2022)

Cost Efficiency: Fintech startups often operate with lower overhead costs compared to traditional financial institutions. (Stulz, 2022) This cost efficiency allows them to offer services at a lower cost, making financial services more accessible to a broader population. It also encourages healthy competition in the financial sector, leading to better services and lower fees.

Innovation in Financial Products: Fintech startups are known for their innovative approach to financial products and services. PhonePe, for example, offers a range of services beyond basic digital payments, including mutual fund investments, insurance, and more. This innovation encourages consumers to explore and use a variety of financial instruments, contributing to the growth of the financial sector. (Nejad, 2022)

Job Creation: The growth of fintech startups often leads to the creation of new jobs, particularly in areas such as software development, data analysis, customer support, and marketing. This job creation contributes to overall economic development by reducing unemployment and stimulating economic activity. (Taiwo et al., 2022)

Efficient Resource Allocation: Fintech platforms leverage data analytics and artificial intelligence to assess credit risk and provide loans more efficiently. This leads to better allocation of resources, as funds are directed to individuals and businesses with a higher likelihood of repayment. Efficient resource allocation is crucial for economic growth.

Economic Efficiency and Productivity: By streamlining financial processes, fintech startups enhance economic efficiency and productivity. This is evident in the faster and more

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convenient ways people can conduct financial transactions, manage investments, and access credit through platforms like PhonePe.

Encouraging Entrepreneurship: Fintech startups often create ecosystems that support entrepreneurship. They may offer APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) and platforms that allow other businesses to build on top of their services, fostering an environment of innovation and entrepreneurship.

In the case of PhonePe, one of the leading digital payment platforms in India, its impact on economic growth is significant, given the large population and the increasing adoption of digital financial services in the country. PhonePe's role in facilitating digital transactions, providing access to financial services, and driving innovation contribute to the overall economic development of the region.

THE CURRENT STATE OF INDIA'S FINANCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE'S INCLUSION.

Economic growth ie is both sustainable and inclusive is a difficult endeavor that necessitates a variety of viewpoints. One of the most important of these is access to basic banking and financial services, such as savings and credit, because it serves to generate a vicious spiral of business opportunities, creativity, and consumerism. Regulatory agencies, formal and informal banks and financial services organizations, telecommunication carriers, credit bureaus, and others are all involved in constructing the necessary financial infrastructure to accomplish the goals outlined below. Even new fintech companies are following the same pattern of constructing infrastructure that allows for adequate growth chances in areas that do not have bank accounts.

Few innovations in banking infrastructure in India

OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

Demonetization - An opportunity for Fintech start up's

With demonetisation and subsequent initiatives, the Indian government has attempted to make the economy less cash-dependent and more computerised, as well as making the banking system more accessible. Going digital is the quickest method to increase financial inclusion and bring more people into the formal banking system, where they can subsequently take advantage of the associated benefits of insurance and investing. There are around 50 million people in India who do not use any sort of formal banking, such as a savings account or a cell phone-based payment system. Having a bank account is required for digital transactions. So, the actual issue here is how to encourage more individuals to create bank accounts so that they can receive digital perks and subsidies. When the government encourages citizens to use less cash, more people are required to have bank accounts, internet access, and cell phones in order to conduct digital transactions. And this is where Aadhaar and the cell phone play a critical role. Out of India's 125 million people, roughly 109 million have signed up for Aadhaar, and at least 100 million have a

cellular number. This is a far bigger amount than the number of people holding bank accounts, which is estimated to be over 70 crores in the most optimistic predictions.

There is the potential to connect at least 30 crore unbanked people through the combined reach of Aadhaar and cell phones. The government has allowed a pilot initiative through the RBI that will speed up the establishment of new bank accounts using Aadhaar and cell phones. Customers can use this method to open limited-functionality bank accounts without having to go through the hassles of visiting a branch, filling out paperwork, and completing the KYC process. They can complete their KYC by confirming themselves with an OTP using their Aadhaar-linked mobile phone. So, there you have it: a digitally opened account that can be accessed quickly, without the need for currency, paper, or even physical presence.

Challenges That Fintech Start-ups Face in India:

Fintech lending companies confront a number of difficulties, including long fund-raising cycles, missed targets, and escalating losses. These problems come primarily as a result of poor lending lifecycle management.

Fintech start-ups in the country encounter a variety of problems on a daily basis.

1. Laws Related issue:

Many rules in India's financial sector inevitably slow Fintech start-ups. These rules are not only difficult to follow, but they also make it impossible for Fintech companies to enter the Indian market. Compliance standards have been enacted as a strict regulatory framework in order to prevent fraud. They, too, are major barriers for new Fintech entrants. Fintech start-ups must meet a slew of standards before they can start doing business.

2. Inhabitants who don't have saving accounts in bank or don't know about it

FinTech's expansion was first delayed by India's poor infrastructure, which included low broadband penetration and educational standards. Despite the fact that the Indian government is taking steps to address these concerns through liberal policies, the gains will take time to be implemented. The truth is that a huge segment of India's population remains untapped, preferring cash transactions to digital transactions. Fintech growth in India is also hampered by the country's low financial literacy. The Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana, for example, was implemented in India to promote financial inclusion.

3. Faith in cash (Cash is a trustworthy or king to invest):

When it comes to everyday transactions, the majority of Indians stick to cash. It is still we know that Indian people always believe in hard cash due to insecurity. Many Indians do not

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believe internet based business even if it is more convenient they still go for cash they think cash is the safest thing to invest even if they go to buy online they still choose cash on delivery for any product that matters.

4. Cyberattacks:

Fintech companies deal with confidential client information. Several cybersecurity risks result in massive monetary losses during online transactions. For customers, these are entirely superfluous. Convenient technology also makes people's online accounts vulnerable to criminals looking to steal their money. FinTech's popularity is rapidly increasing. Hackers are a menace to fintech firms; thus, they must be protected. A significant amount of financial data about individuals and corporations is made public through digital means. This increases the risk of a data breach.

5. Lack of support from administrative:

FinTech firms in India face a serious lack of government/legislative support and incentives to protect their financial sector interests. This could be discouraging for new Fintech players. Fin-Techs are vital to supporting economic growth, and they must be given all of the tools they need to flourish.

PhonePe is a digital payments platform that supports over 11 languages and was launched in December 2015. It was one of the first payment apps to use the Unified Payments Interface (UPI), and it was also the first UPI payment app to reach the billion-transaction threshold. Users can use the app to receive and send money, check bank balances, make POS payments, acquire gold, and complete a variety of activities such as phone recharges, DTH payments, electricity, gas, and other bill payments. Furthermore, PhonePe is a popular UPI app that is accepted by the majority of Indian retailers and allows users to book rides, order food, make purchases, and more all over the internet.

PhonePe - Business

In just the last 12 months, digital payment transactions have increased by roughly 76 percent, including a large number of first-time digital payment users. India's digital payments market is expected to reach \$700 billion by 2022, according to reports.

PhonePe is the market leader in this massive Indian digital payment business, with a market share of 46.3 percent, while Google Pay is in second place with a market share of 36.4 percent, according to data from December 7, 2021.

IMAGE BY GOOGLE

PhonePe - Investors and Funding

To date, PhonePe has raised \$1.7 billion in 13 rounds of investment. The company just completed a \$350 million funding round with Walmart, which was an expansion of the \$700 million investment round announced in Dec 2020

Partnerships - PhonePe

In the seven years that PhonePe has been in business, it has seen far too many partnerships. Here are a few of the most significant ones:

On July 2, 2021, PhonePe and Axis Bank will collaborate on a UPI multi-bank concept. It has previously partnered with Yes Bank.

On July 7, 2020, Ola partnered with PhonePe to accept Ola payments through the PhonePe app and wallet.

On July 6, 2021, PhonePe will work with Flipkart to digitise cash-on-delivery payments.

On September 10, 2021, PhonePe became KBFC's official payment partner.

On December 20, 2021, Edelweiss General Insurance partnered with PhonePe to offer digital automobile insurance solutions. Google pay, Paytm, MobiKwik, Bharat-Pe etc are PhonePe's main-competitors.

PhonePe – Expansion

In December of 2015, PhonePe was founded. Flipkart purchased PhonePe in 2016. Flipkart paid between \$10 and \$20 million for the app in 2016, and it now has a market capitalization of over \$5.5 billion at the end of 2021. This is an obvious reference to the company's expansion. The first UPI-based app to reach ten million downloads in 2017. On both the Apple App Store and the Google Play Store, it consistently ranks among the top finance apps. PhonePe grew to become India's leading provider of UPI transactions. It reached a milestone of 1 million app transactions per day in 2017. When it came to growth in 2019, PhonePe was one of the winners. With an annual growth rate of 857.22 percent, PhonePe dominated the

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year. From 2018 to 2019, all of the top payment applications rose by 88 percent. PhonePe is on the verge of breaking new milestones in July, with total transactions approaching 1.5 billion, while Google Pay crosses the 1 billion mark for the first time.

PHONEPE COMPANY'S CURRENT MARKET SHARE:

In 2021, the PhonePe app will have 42.55 percent of the market share in the country. During the month, PhonePe handled client transactions totaling INR 2.34 lakh crore. It reported a 45 percent market share in April

On a month-over-month (MoM) basis, PhonePe's transactions increased by about 7% and their value by nearly 5% in January. PhonePe has taken the #1 spot for the second time in a row.

Conclusion

PhonePe's platform had 902.03 million transactions in December, totalling Rs 1.82 trillion. With 853.53 million transactions totalling Rs 1.77 trillion, PhonePe comes in second, accounting for over 37% of the UPI market in terms of volume. These apps have a combined market share of 79.13 percent in terms of volume and more than 85 percent in terms of value. The landscape of digital payments has changed drastically ever since the demonetization at the end of 2016. PhonePe is a digital wallet and online payment app that allows users to pay bills, transfer money, invest in mutual funds and gold, buy life insurance and make instant payments to your favorite online and offline stores via wallet or UPI. Only recently, PhonePe earmarked INR 8,000 crore marketing budget to penetrate deeper into the country, whilst simultaneously taking on the rising competition. As part of the deal, the company signed two very popular Bollywood celebrities- Aamir Khan and Alia Bhatt for its endorsements. The

company aims to add more than 100 million people every year till the goal of 500 million verified users is reached. Over the years, PhonePe has added many sources of revenue to its business and now it isn't just a digital wallet/UPI-based payment platform. PhonePe generates revenue from commissions from a variety of sources like Mobile recharges and postpaid bill payments. Utility bill payments (gas, electricity and water), DTH recharge, Selling Insurance, Selling Gold, By charging merchants a commission on every sale through PhonePe UPI/Wallet, Mutual funds, Bus, train and flight reservations

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